

NIVA WP 3 –Official Statistics Slovenia

interview

Date: 15 January 2021 - 9h 30 – 10 h 45

Location: Teams meeting

Stakeholder description

1. Organisation name: Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia
2. Person name:
3. Person position /role :
 - removed for privacy reasons: consultant in agricultural statistics + work on GIS
 - removed for privacy reasons: consultant in agricultural statistics ; work on agricultural census and use of administrative sources
4. What is the general purpose of the organisation?

The Statistical Office of Slovenia is in charge to produce statistics on all kinds of topics: demography, economics, agriculture, environment.... Most of statistics are based on legal acts, and all have methodology description.

Our statistics are used by public decision makers, researchers, students and general public. Statistics about agriculture are not the most visited because they target narrower population of interest, but agriculture has a big financial impact for the whole EU (it is the most costly EU policy).

5. What are the activities related to agriculture in general? What are the activities requiring use of data about agriculture?

Every 10 year we conduct agricultural census: all agricultural holdings (production above certain threshold) in each EU country have to be surveyed, and different variables are collected and then sent to Eurostat, which disseminates the data e.g. number of animals, types of crop – it is an EU based regulation (Integrated Farm Statistics) - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2018/1091/oj> -

Agricultural census is about what previously happened but in agricultural department we also conducting some forecasts.

We collect data from statistical surveys (mostly computer assisted phone surveys) and through administrative source. IACS is one of the administrative sources that we have been using for 10 years at least.

Statistics rely heavily on IACS data. We consider it of good quality and we are happy with it.

User experience – User requirements

1. What current IACS data do you need?

- Reference Parcels

Yes, we use them. We are interested in the location, size and land cover information (arable land, permanent crops, permanent grassland). We have a system of farmer block. The identifier is also useful, to make the link to farmer plots or to holdings.

This LPIS data has to be clean by beginning of June for the farmer declarations.

- Agricultural parcels

Yes, we use them. We are interested in the crop type (around 100 values in Slovenia including arable land and permanent crops). We are involved in the crop type list preparation, we can make requests to the Paying Agency, we have good cooperation (even if not perfect).

We are also interested in the identifier to make the link to the holding and to track parcels.

Data is available on-line all the time. In practice, we collect first provisional data on 25 May that will be used to assess and forecast future crop production. Then, we collect final data by end of July.

Each year we use IACS data, each year we produce statistics after it. We also compare data from previous years e.g. crop rotation (around 3 years) or for permanent grasslands (3 or 5 years ago).

IACS data is covering roughly 94% of agricultural area, cultivated by agricultural holdings.

- Landscape features

We are lacking info on woodlands outside forests: no one is in charge of collecting them. There is some data in LPIS but not exhaustive and not detailed enough.

For the agricultural statistics that we are currently producing, we do not need data about landscape features.

- Farmer declaration

Because of our special position, as statistical office, we can access the details of the farmer declaration about the schemes the farmer applies to, which programme he is included in e.g. if he is an ecological farmer – whatever subsidies he applies for.

We don't publish this data as agricultural statistics, the Ministry of Agricultural Holdings is producing this kind of statistics, this is more a financial aspect of whole system.

- Animals

Yes, there is a central Register of Animals (not IACS data) for bovine, pigs, equine, goats, beehives. Farmers have to provide data on number of animals they breed on a specific date, it is collected by admin body.

- Beneficiaries

Yes, most of the agricultural holdings are included in the Register of Agricultural Holdings ; from that we get all what we need e.g. location of farm, farmers address, tax number, social security number, holding uses etc. – all info is recorded in this register and IACS data connects with this register

Around 8% of farmers are out of IACS.

We produce statistics on age, gender, education ... of farmers and most of the data comes from administrative sources. Data on labour input is coming from statistical surveys and is complemented with administrative sources.

- Quality controls

We are in touch with Paying Agencies, we know their control method; we trust them to validate data and we don't do additional direct controls (only statistical editing). In case of discrepancy, we contact the Paying Agency to clarify the issue. But this case is quite rare.

- Entitlements

It is unsure if this system applies in Slovenia. Most subsidies are area based.

However, we are tracking the information about the kinds of schemes because some schemes may influence farmers. A new subsidy may entail increase of some production (e.g. 2019 – farmers got more money to plant pulses (a scheme) and we track when this happens and why – this means that the area of crop increases in a certain year and we need to know why)

- Payments

There are statistics about them but is related to the economic accounts, not to the agricultural census. These statistics provide information at least on the value of paid money for each pillar and may be more details.

FADN is an administrative body also collecting data.

1. What potential future IACS data do you need?

- Farm Registry

In Slovenia there is a project on this topic; system is under on-going development. Farmers would get some application – fill in areas, fertilisers...

We would be interested in producing stats on pesticides, fertilisers etc.

- Crop classification & Traffic lights (EO monitoring)

We were examining the options to use remote sensing, but with current Eurostat accuracy requirements most satellite data (e.g. Sentinel) would not be accurate enough for us: agricultural parcels are generally small in Slovenia.

We have interest for results from satellite images but fear about accuracy; may be in future if Eurostat rules change.

- Geotagged photos

It is out of our scope. We use the data coming from the controls done in IACS.

- Agro-environmental indicators

We already publish indicators on gross nutrient balance; the methodology is quite complex, calculations are done on Agricultural Institute.

We might be interested by the indicators proposed by NIVA as a new or additional data source. Either in the methodology to compute ourselves the indicators or by taking directly the indicator values from IACS if available.

Opinion about data sharing principles

1. What data do you think should be publicly available for use?

Public availability is a good thing (personal opinion).

2. What data do you think should not be shared and should only be used by Paying Agencies?

- What has made you feel this way/why do you think this way?

As official statistics, we do not disclose any individual information (only aggregates). Sharing of the data by the Paying Agencies is out of our scope (we have the right to access to whatever is necessary for our work). In Slovenia, most farmers are physical persons.

3. Who do you think most benefits from partially or open data sharing?

- Can you explain why you feel this way?

Society in general; this is why the work of Statistical office is very useful.

4. Do you have any idea about how the process of data sharing from farmer to wider stakeholder groups can be improved?

Progress may be done in data collection. IACS data should be consistent with needs of Eurostat statistics; EU is providing both the rules for IACS data collection and for the variables to be considered in statistics but there is not always a 1:1 link. We need to have continuous cooperation, this is on-going process with Paying Agencies to adjust but it would be easier if coming from coherent top down decisions. For instance, Eurostat needs data on open field meaning area of vegetation or on market gardening but this type of data is lacking from IACS.

Another progress might come from making life easier for farmers regarding their declarations. Currently, they have to fill their declaration for IACS but also to supply information to other registries. This is significant administrative burden.